

MODERN PROBLEMS OF PROVIDING THE POPULATION WITH AFFORDABLE AND HIGH-QUALITY MEDICINES

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Relevance: The sustainable development of the pharmaceutical sector plays a decisive role in ensuring public health. In the pharmaceutical market of Uzbekistan, high dependence on imports, the inflow of counterfeit and low-quality drugs, underdeveloped local production, and weak quality control remain pressing problems. Therefore, the issue of supplying the population with affordable and high-quality medicines is of both scientific and practical importance.

Research Objective. The purpose of this study is to examine the measures taken to meet the population's need for affordable and high-quality medicines, to restrict the production of counterfeit drugs, to support local manufacturers, and to reduce import dependence.

Methods. This scientific work used official sources of the Pharmaceutical Products Safety Center and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results. In our republic, by Presidential Decree of January 23, 2024 (UP-20), manufacturers and sellers of medicines and medical products were made directly responsible for the quality, safety, and effectiveness of their products; special rules of state supervision were introduced in the sector. Under this document, regional structures were reorganized, and the "Good Practices Center" system was established. A "roadmap" for 2024–2025 was approved, and funds were allocated to accelerate new projects. A government decision dated January 10, 2024 (PP-14) was adopted to support the production of the most demanded pharmaceutical products and new investment projects, attract investments, expand the introduction of international standards such as GMP, and increase production volumes. Strict measures on quality and safety (after the Marion Biotech case): responsible officials were punished, compensations were determined - this accelerated the policy of strengthening control and reducing low-quality imports.

In the first quarter of 2025, the Central Body for Certification of Medical Products of the Pharmaceutical Products Safety Center officially issued 307 certificates of conformity for 770 series of medicines, medical devices, and medical equipment totaling 119,651,012 conditional packages. Additionally, 49 series of 408,521 conditional packages of medicines, medical devices, and equipment were found to be non-compliant with regulatory requirements. Illegal production of counterfeit drugs was detected in various regions of the country. In particular, in the Mirzo Ulugbek district of Tashkent, powdered raw materials used in drug preparation (180 kg), nearly 3,000 boxes of tablets and capsules, and 133 bottles of handmade drugs were discovered. In Kashkadarya region, medicines were being produced at home. In Gulistan, 10,481 expired medicines and medical devices worth a total of 435.9 million UZS were stored with the intent to sell and were confiscated as material evidence.

Conclusion. To support local manufacturers:

- Prioritize GMP-certified domestic enterprises in state procurements and long-term contracts (expanding existing mechanisms).
- Simplify fast-track registration and authorization processes for medicines, especially local analogues.

- Provide preferential loans, grants, and investment subsidies; establish free economic zones and pharmaceutical parks.
- Expand bioequivalence and laboratory infrastructure (GLP, ISO/IEC 17025) to enable fast and affordable preclinical and clinical trials for domestic generics.
- Create a fast-track lane in the state register for local products.
- Apply transparent reference pricing in price lists.
- Provide grants for SRA-compliant documentation to support exports.